

Size-free one-class classification approach using probabilistic local cluster balance

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ABSTRACT

One-class classification (OCC) is a supervised classification problem where the training data is solely one class. However, existing OCC algorithms must resize input images to a fixed size, which may lead to information loss. This paper proposes the first size-free OCC algorithm: one-class probabilistic local cluster balance (OCPLCB). The proposed method can extract feature vectors without resizing. OCPLCB applies k-means clustering to sliding windows in images. Subsequently, a feature vector is extracted by dividing cluster balance by the number of sliding windows. Finally, the feature vectors are classified by traditional OCC algorithms. Additionally, this study avoids hyperparameter tuning by combining multiple hyperparameters. The proposed method shows fair areas under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) scores in grayscale datasets without deep learning. The discussion section provides the benefits of size-free OCC, limitations, and potential future work. Source code is uploaded at <https://github.com/ToshiHayashi/OCPLCB>

1. Introduction

Supervised classification trains the classification models from labeled datasets. However, these models cannot classify data into unseen classes not included in the dataset. One-class classification (OCC) is a supervised classification problem where the training data consists of only one class. OCC aims to classify the data into one class and other classes. This approach is promising for detecting unseen classes.

The general OCC approach computes arbitrary score functions for a single class. The score functions are categorized into normal/seen score and abnormal/unseen score. Subsequently, a threshold value is determined to distinguish between one class and other classes. Various OCC algorithms have been proposed in the literature [1–4]. However, these models are not robust for different input sizes.

This paper aims to develop a size-free OCC algorithm for images. Size-free refers to the ability to process (learn and classify) the unresized inputs without the system errors. Traditional benchmark datasets [5–8] collected images with a fixed height and width. However, these datasets sacrificed the normality of other aspects, such as resolution or image entropy. Developing a size-free algorithm could normalize these aspects, rather than the size.

For this purpose, this study uses One-Class Local Cluster Balance (OCLCB) as baseline. OCLCB was proposed as a feature extrac-

tion method for time-series data [9]. The motivation was to stop re-training the model for different signal lengths. The main idea was to apply k-means clustering [10] to sliding windows and to use the clustering result as feature vectors for the signals. This feature was called Local Cluster Balance (LCB), referring to the number of clusters for sliding windows. However, the LCB features were sensitive to the number of sliding windows. Size-free OCC should extract the feature vectors that are invariant to number of the sliding windows.

Accordingly, this paper proposes a one-class probabilistic local cluster balance (OCPLCB). The idea is to represent an image as the probability of clusters within sliding windows of the image. In other words, the proposed method divides the LCB feature by the number of sliding windows. Probability can achieve size-free because it is invariant to the number of sliding windows. The extension is non-trivial because it provides a new methodological perspective on OCC research for size-free image datasets.

This paper has the following contributions:

- This study developed the first size-free image OCC algorithm, which can learn and classify various sizes of images without system errors. Moreover, the proposed method can classify various image shapes, not limited to a rectangle.

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- Another novelty is the probabilistic local cluster balance (PLCB) feature, which represents the probability of clusters within sliding windows in an image.
- The experiments with size-free datasets, namely randomly resized MNIST(RR-MNIST) and randomly resized CIFAR10 (RR-CIFAR10), and the original size X-ray image dataset.
- The experiment results suggest that color-based features do not contribute to OCC in image data. This information is important for future work.

The paper is organized as follows: [Section 2](#) summarizes related work, and [Section 3](#) proposes the OCPLCB algorithm. [Sections 4](#) and [5](#) provide experiment results and discussions, respectively. Finally, [Section 6](#) gives the conclusion and future work.

2. Related work

This section summarizes related works. [Subsection 2.1](#) describes the general OCC framework, while [subsection 2.2](#) mentions clustering algorithms in image data. Additionally, [Subsection 2.3](#) explains ensemble learning, and [subsection 2.4](#) mentions size-free algorithms.

2.1. One-class classification

OCC aims to classify data into a single class or the remaining classes. OCC algorithms train the score functions from the training dataset. Score is the normality belonging to one class, referred to as the normal/seen score, and the dissimilarity from one class, known as the anomaly/unknown score. Subsequently, a threshold value is determined to distinguish between one class and other classes.

The general OCC framework is as follows:

$$OCC(X) = \begin{cases} One(score(X) \geq \lambda) \\ Other(score(X) < \lambda) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where λ corresponds to a threshold value. Moreover, the score is the likelihood of belonging to one class, including reversed dissimilarity values. Most studies [11,12] did not determine clear threshold values. Instead, the algorithm uses the Area Under the receiver operating characteristic (AUC) curve, calculated without determining the threshold. AUC corresponds to the degree to which the score function separates one class from other classes. The researchers developed several OCC algorithms for the feature [1–3], image [11], and time series [12,13]. This paper is related to feature and image data described in the following subsections.

OCC algorithms are roughly categorized into five types [14]: boundary-based, distance-based, probability-based, fake-based, and subtask-based approaches. The boundary-based approach computes the boundary between one class and other classes. The distance-based approach computes distances/similarities from one class. A probability-based approach computes the probability that a sample belongs to one class. A fake-based approach generates pseudo-samples corresponding to other classes and executes binary classification between the real class and fake classes. The subtask-based approach uses errors of subtasks as the score of OCC.

Boundary, distance, and probability-based approaches handle only feature vectors, while fake and subtasks are applied to all data types. Moreover, there is a feature extraction method that combines feature extraction and feature OCC algorithms. Accordingly, all types of OCC algorithms can process all data types.

2.1.1. One-class classification for feature vector

Existing feature OCC methods are categorized into boundary-based, distance-based, and probability-based approaches. Boundary-based approach computes the boundary in feature vector space. Distance-based approach use distance/similarity metrics. Probability-

based approach computes the probability that samples belong to one class.

Tax et al. [15,16] proposed Support Vector Data Description (SVDD), which computes a hypersphere around the data distribution. The hypothesis is that data from one class is within the sphere. Schölkopf et al. [1] proposed a One-Class Support Vector Machine (OCSVM), which maps the data into a kernel space and computes a hyperplane separating the mapped feature vectors from the origin, serving as an indicator of outliers.

Moreover, the Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [2] computes local densities calculated by distances from the nearest samples. The hypothesis is that outliers have lower local densities than their nearest training samples.

Besides, the Isolation Forest (IF) [3] applies a random tree structure to detect outliers. The hypothesis is that normal samples gather within the specific leaves, while outliers are isolated. Random splits will perform as boundary.

In addition, the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) [17] is a clustering technique based on Gaussian distributions. GMM can compute normal scores from the Gaussian distribution fitted to training data. Many researchers combine these OCC algorithms with feature extraction methods.

2.1.2. Feature extraction-based OCC

One general image OCC approach is to combine feature extraction and classic OCC algorithms. Feature extraction is the process of representing arbitrary data types as feature vectors. Several feature extraction methods have been proposed for image data, such as histograms [18–20], bag-of-visual-words [21,22], and deep learning [11].

A histogram is a statistical chart to visualize the distribution of continuous data. In the context of an image dataset, a histogram is related to the pixel values. Fu et al. [18] combined histogram-based feature and OCSVM for object tracking. In which the dimensions of the histograms are adaptively selected based on the size of the initial bounding boxes. However, different sizes of bounding boxes were handled by different OCSVM models. Moreover, histogram-based features have been applied to image analysis in food sciences, such as the authentication of coffee [19] and tea [20].

Bag of visual words [21] is a technique to represent images as a balance of visual words. A visual word is an arbitrary concept to represent an image. The general idea is to split the images into smaller subparts (referred to as patches [23,24] or sliding windows) and compute visual words for each subpart. Finally, a feature vector is created by the frequency of visual words within the image. Some researchers represent images to texts [22]. The proposed method belongs to the bag-of-visual-words framework, computed from clustering results over sliding windows.

Deep learning is a technique to automatically extract important features for minimizing the errors of tasks. Luff et al. [11] proposed deep-SVDD, which combined an autoencoder (AE)-based feature and SVDD. However, the AE specializes in feature vectors for the reconstruction task, which is not effective in classification. Chen et al. [25] applied a self-supervised classification model for extracting feature vectors specialized for classification tasks. Reiss et al. [26,27] adapted feature vectors from pretrained classification models learned from ImageNet, which contain 1000 classes. A pretrained model can represent the feature vectors for 1000 classes, which is effective in tackling the OCC problem. However, the solution is no longer OCC because the algorithm learns more than 1000 classes in total.

Patch anomaly detection [23,24] is an AD technique that handles patches in images. Lee [23] applied AE for patches, while Man et al. [24] proposed GAN-based filters for patches.

This paper applies clustering to sliding windows and computes the probability of clusters as feature vectors. Apart from other methods, the feature vector is size-independent, allowing it to extract the same-dimensional feature vectors from images of varying sizes.

2.1.3. Other image OCC algorithms

This subsection summarizes fake-based and subtask-based OCC algorithms. These methods are dissimilar to the proposal, yet comparative methods. The fake approach generates pseudo-anomalies and executes binary classification between a target class and a fake class. The researchers proposed several strategies to generate fake anomalies, including centered Gaussian noise [28], generative adversarial networks [29], and diffusion models [30]. Moreover, Hendrycks et al. [31] proposed outlier exposure, which imports other datasets as fake outliers. Liznerski et al. [32] highlighted that accessing a few outliers is enough to outperform OCC algorithms. However, importing other datasets allows access to additional classes, which conflicts with learning from a single class.

The subtask-based approach uses errors of subtasks as the normal scores for OCC models. The general process is to train an arbitrary model for an arbitrary subtask derived from a single class. The hypothesis is that the model cannot solve the subtask for other classes because these classes did not contribute to training. In other words, the model will show less error for samples from one class than for those from other classes. The researchers proposed several subtasks, such as reconstruction, transformation, knowledge distillation, and classification.

- The reconstruction subtask aims to reconstruct the input. The error is the distance between the inputs and the reconstructed inputs. A common approach utilizes an autoencoder (AE) [4] and its variants [33–36]
- The transformation subtask [37] aims to create the ideal outputs from the inputs. The error is the distance metric between the model outputs and the ideal outputs.
- The knowledge distillation subtask [38,39] aims to transfer the behavior of a large model to a smaller one. The error is a distance metric between the outputs of two models.
- The classification subtask aims to classify self-labeled images created by editing the original images (rotation [40], geometric transformation [41], shifting instances and applying filters [42]). The score of OCC is classification accuracy of subtask.
- Contrastive learning subtask [42] aims to create the agreement between different views. The score is agreement, referring to the similarity/dissimilarity metrics. Moreover, view refers to arbitrary image transformations, such as shifting, cutout, Sobel, noise, blur, perm, and rotation.

Tack et al. [42] combined the classification subtask and contrastive learning subtasks. Their method is the best in the pure OCC algorithms for image data. However, existing OCC algorithms have to resize the input for handling

2.2. Clustering algorithms

Clustering is an unsupervised learning to separate samples into groups. Several techniques have been proposed [43]. Clustering algorithms can be categorized based on whether they create models. This study requires a clustering model because the outputs should be consistent in the training and testing stages.

Additionally, clustering techniques have found applications in image data analysis. Superpixel [44] segments an image into regions based on similarity metrics computed from color and spatial information. The task is clustering of pixels.

Deep clustering [45] trains neural networks without class labels using image clustering results as proxy labels for supervised learning. This approach allows the model to specialize feature vectors for classification without annotation.

This paper applies K-means clustering [10] to sliding windows and compute the probabilities of clusters within the image. Such a probability is used as a feature vector for images.

2.3. Ensemble learning

Ensemble learning [46,47] is a technique that combines multiple classifiers, known as base learners. Dietterich [46] explained three reasons why ensemble learning outperforms base learners. The first reason is statistical: ensemble learning averages base learners, reducing the risk of selecting the worst base learner. The second reason is the computational aspect; many base learners may be stuck in local optima, whereas an ensemble can avoid this problem. The third reason is the representational aspect: an ensemble can create a boundary that a single base learner cannot. In addition, Bustillo et al. [47] added the fourth reason for avoiding hyperparameter tuning. Ensemble can combine all hyperparameters, so users do not have to select hyperparameters. This aspect is especially helpful in the OCC problem because accessing other classes will change OCC problems to binary/multi-class classification problems [48].

Ensemble learning has been categorized into several types, such as bagging [49], voting [50], boosting [51], and stacking [52]. Bagging [49] and voting [50] combine outputs of base learners in parallel. Boosting [51] connects base learners sequentially: the first model learns from samples, while subsequent models learn from the errors of previous models. In addition, stacking [52] is a technique that uses model outputs as feature vectors for an ensemble model. The proposed PLCB feature is positioned as a variant of stacking, where the clustering results of sliding windows are combined to create feature vectors for OCC models.

2.4. Size-free algorithms

The existing size-free algorithms are limited. He et al. [53] proposed Spatial Pyramid Pooling for a fixed input size. They trained neural networks on multi-size inputs of 224×224 and 180×180 . Spatial Pyramid pooling was used in the well-known ResNet architecture [54]. However, deep learning libraries like Keras and PyTorch do not support variable input sizes. Accordingly, deep learning algorithms require resizing.

Size-free algorithms are used in object detection because they must classify bounding boxes of varying sizes. However, these techniques are developed for multi-class classification purposes. On the other hand, this paper considers a size-free OCC algorithm.

Fu et al. [18] combined histogram-based feature and OCSVM for object tracking. In which the dimension of the histogram was adaptively selected according to the size of the initial bounding boxes. However, different OCSVM models handled bounding boxes of different sizes. Therefore, the paper did not develop the size-free OCC algorithm.

Spanhol et al. [55] trained convolutional neural networks (CNN) on patches. Subsequently, the patch outputs are combined to obtain the image-level output. In this way, the algorithm can be size-free when the entire image size is larger than the patch size. The idea is related to bagging in ensemble learning [49]. However, CNN was not OCC.

This study proposes size-free algorithms based on clustering sliding windows. Regarding the use of sliding windows, the most similar techniques are deep learning architectures, such as convolution and pooling layers.

Deep learning layers aim to minimize loss functions for specific tasks, while the proposed method does not control the clustering results. This aspect could offer new insights into image feature extraction.

Table 1 highlights the research gap between related work and the proposal. Although size-free methods have been proposed in the literature, existing OCC algorithms are not size-free. Therefore, this paper has a novelty in developing a size-free OCC algorithm.

3. The proposed method

This section proposes size-free OCC algorithm, OCPLCB. Fig. 1 shows the OCPLCB framework, consisting of training and testing stages. Subsection 3.1 explains the process to extract the PLCB feature. Subsections 3.2 and 3.3 describe the training and testing stages, respectively.

Table 1
Research Gap.

Methods	Data	Task	Size-free
Image OCCs	Image	OCC	No
Size free methods	Image	Multi class	Yes
OCLCB	Time series	OCC	No
OCPLCB	Image	OCC	Yes

Fig. 1. OCPLCB framework.

Fig. 2. Probabilistic local cluster balance feature.

3.1. Probabilistic local cluster balance

Probabilistic local cluster balance (PLCB) is a feature vector extracted from an image. Fig. 2 visualizes the PLCB feature extraction process. The proposed method extracts sliding windows from the image and applies a clustering algorithm to these windows. Subsequently, the clustering result is summarized as local cluster balance (LCB), which is a vector referring to a distribution of clusters for sliding windows. Finally, one can obtain PLCB by dividing LCB by the number of sliding windows. In summary, PLCB is the probability of clusters for sliding windows in the image.

The following paragraph describes the formal method. Let X as an image:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} X_{11} & \cdots & X_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{M1} & \cdots & X_{MN} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where M and N are related to image size. The proposed method extracts sliding windows W from X :

$$W = \begin{bmatrix} W_{11} & \cdots & W_{1(N-d+1)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ W_{(M-d+1)1} & \cdots & W_{(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$W_{mn} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{mn} & \cdots & X_{m(n+d-1)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{(m+d-1)n} & \cdots & X_{(m+d-1)(n+d-1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where d is the window size, and m and n are indices in sliding windows. Moreover, there is another potential hyperparameter, step size s . This study sets $s = 1$ to cover all possible sliding windows. Otherwise, the proposed method extracts only windows W_{mn} that satisfy $(m \bmod s = 1$ and $n \bmod s = 1)$ from the image.

Subsequently, an arbitrary clustering model f is applied to sliding windows:

$$\begin{cases} f : W_{mn} \rightarrow C_k, C_k \in C, \\ C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k, \dots, C_K\}, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where C represents the set of clusters and K indicates the number of clusters. Note that sliding windows are reshaped to $d \times d$ -dimensional vectors. Let $Cmap$ as the clustering results of sliding windows in a single image:

$$Cmap = \begin{bmatrix} Cmap_{11} & \cdots & Cmap_{1(N-d+1)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Cmap_{(M-d+1)1} & \cdots & Cmap_{(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$Cmap_{mn} = f(W_{mn}) \quad (7)$$

Local cluster balance (LCB) [9] is a K -dimensional vector, calculated by counting clusters in $Cmap$:

$$LCB = (|C_1 \in Cmap|, \dots, |C_k \in Cmap|, \dots, |C_K \in Cmap|) \quad (8)$$

Apart from the original OCLCB [9], this study modifies LCB to probability, namely PLCB. One can compute PLCB by dividing LCB by the number of sliding windows:

$$PLCB = \frac{LCB}{(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \quad (9)$$

PLCB and LCB are equivalent for the same size image, while PLCB is flexible for input size or shape. Finally, PLCB is classified by an arbitrary OCC algorithm for feature data. that are written as:

$$OCC(PLCB) = \begin{cases} One(score(PLCB) \geq \lambda) \\ Other(score(PLCB) < \lambda) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where λ is the threshold value, and the score corresponds to the likelihood belonging to one class. The original OCLCB [9] computed the score as a distance metric between LCB and average of LCBs in training dataset:

$$score(PLCB) = -distance(PLCB, Avg(PLCBtr)). \quad (11)$$

Moreover, this paper applies the existing OCC algorithms, such as OCSVM [1], LOF [2], IF[3], and GMM [17] to PLCB features. The following subsections describe the training and testing stages.

3.2. Training stage

The training stage creates a clustering model from sliding windows, represents training images as PLCB feature, and train arbitrary OCC model for PLCB features. The input is training images Xtr :

$$Xtr = [Xtr_1, Xtr_2, \dots, Xtr_i, \dots], \quad (12)$$

where i is the ID of the images. The sliding windows Wtr are extracted from all Xtr . Let Wtr_i as sliding windows from i th image Xtr_i :

$$Wtr_i = \begin{bmatrix} Wtr_{i,11} & \cdots & Wtr_{i,1(N-d+1)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Wtr_{i,(M-d+1)1} & \cdots & Wtr_{i,(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where the structure of Wtr_{imn} refers to Eq. 4.

The next step is to train an arbitrary clustering model f (see Eq. 5) from sliding windows. The model is applied to all sliding windows. As for Wtr_i , clustering results can be written as:

$$Cmap_i = \begin{bmatrix} Cmap_{i,11} & \cdots & Cmap_{i,1(N-d+1)} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ Cmap_{i,(M-d+1)1} & \cdots & Cmap_{i,(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$Cmap_{i,mn} = f(Wtr_{i,mn}) \quad (15)$$

Afterwards, the $PLCB_i$ is computed as probability of clusters:

$$PLCB_i = \frac{(|C_1 \in Cmap_i|, \dots, |C_k \in Cmap_i|, \dots, |C_K \in Cmap_i|)}{(M-d+1)(N-d+1)}, \quad (16)$$

where the numerator is a vector, representing cluster balances, while the denominator is the number of sliding windows. As a result, the set of PLCBs are obtained as:

$$PLCBtr = [PLCB_1, PLCB_2, \dots, PLCB_i, \dots], \quad (17)$$

Afterward, OCC model is trained from PLCB features:

$$Training : PLCBtr \rightarrow OCC, \quad (18)$$

Note that the above equation is written in abstract way. This process applies an arbitrary OCC algorithms.

3.3. Testing stage

The testing stage extracts the LCB feature from an image and computes an unseen score with a trained score function. Finally, OCC is executed based on the threshold value. Let Xte as a testing image:

$$Xte = \begin{bmatrix} Xte_{11} & \cdots & Xte_{1N} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ Xte_{M1} & \cdots & Xte_{MN} \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Sliding windows Wte are extracted in the same way as the training stage:

$$Wte = \begin{bmatrix} Wte_{11} & \cdots & Wte_{1(N-d+1)} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ Wte_{(M-d+1)1} & \cdots & Wte_{(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Clustering model f is applied to sliding windows:

$$Cmap_{te} = \begin{bmatrix} Cmap_{te,11} & \cdots & Cmap_{te,1(N-d+1)} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ Cmap_{te,(M-d+1)1} & \cdots & Cmap_{te,(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

$$Cmap_{te,mn} = f(Wte_{mn}) \quad (22)$$

Afterwards, $PLCB_{te}$ is computed from clustering results:

$$PLCB_{te} = \frac{(|C_1 \in Cmap_{te}|, \dots, |C_k \in Cmap_{te}|, \dots, |C_K \in Cmap_{te}|)}{(M-d+1)(N-d+1)} \quad (23)$$

Finally, OCC model classifies $PLCB_{te}$ into one or other classes:

$$Y_{te} = OCC(PLCB_{te}) = \begin{cases} One(score(PLCB_{te}) \geq \lambda) \\ Other(score(PLCB_{te}) < \lambda) \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

4. Experiments

This section supplies the experimental results. [Subsection 4.1](#) provides information about the datasets used in the experiment; [subsection 4.2](#) reports the experimental results. Moreover, [subsection 4.3](#) compares various OCC algorithms in the fixed image size. [Subsection 4.4](#) demonstrates the advantage of OCPLCB in datasets, including images of different sizes.

Table 2
Dataset description.

Dataset	Class	Training	Testing	Shape
MNIST	10	60000	10000	28 × 28 × 1
FMNIST	10	60000	10000	28 × 28 × 1
CIFAR10	10	50000	10000	32 × 32 × 3
CIFAR100	100 (20)	50000	10000	32 × 32 × 3
Kuzushiji49	49	232365	38547	28 × 28 × 1
X-Ray chest(Resize)	2	5216	624	32 × 32 × 1
X-Ray chest(Original size)	2	5216	624	M × N × 1
RR-MNIST	10	60000	10000	M × M × 1
RR-CIFAR10	10	50000	10000	M × M × 3

4.1. Datasets and evaluation metric

This study utilized three well-known benchmark image datasets: MNIST[5], Fashion-MNIST (FMNIST) [6], and CIFAR10 [7]. These datasets consist of images annotated to ten different classes. Moreover, CIFAR100 [7] contains color images for 100 classes grouped into 20 superclasses. This study experimented with superclasses. In addition, the Kuzushiji49 dataset [8] includes images corresponding to 49 hiragana characters written in Japanese historical documents. Besides, X-ray chest images [56,57] were employed as real-world data for pneumonia classification, comprising two classes: normal and pneumonia. The original images have various sizes, which were resized to 32 × 32 × 1.

[Table 2](#) provides information on each dataset, including the number of images, the number of classes, and the image shapes. Resized datasets are selected for the comparison, while other datasets are selected for size-free experiments.

These datasets are already split into training and test sets. The OCC experiment treats a single class as one class and the remaining classes as other classes. Moreover, the training dataset is modified to include only a single class. The OCC models learn the training set and are applied to the test set. The above process is repeated to treat each class as the target class.

This study selected the Area under the ROC curve (AUC) as an evaluation metric, which can be computed from all possible thresholds. Moreover, other OCC algorithms have been evaluated with AUC. The experiment is generally single run, while the experiment of X-ray images was executed for five times.

4.2. Hyperparameter analysis

The proposed method includes two numerical hyperparameters: the sliding window size d and the number of clusters K . Moreover, the algorithm requires two categorical parameters: the clustering algorithm and the OCC algorithms.

This study selects K-means [10] as a clustering algorithm because the algorithm has less time and space complexity [58] and does not cause long-time processing or memory errors. Other clustering algorithms, GMM [17] and Birch [59] were tried out in the experiments. However, both algorithms gave memory errors with large sliding windows.

As for OCC algorithms, Classic refers to the score function of the original OCLCB [9] (see Eq. 11). Moreover, OCSVM, LOF, IF, and GMM were imported from the sklearn package [60].

This section compares these parameters in terms of AUC scores. [Table 3](#) summarizes the investigated parameters. The experiment results suggest that having more K generally leads to better AUC scores. However, increasing K requires larger memory space because K corresponds to the number of dimensions for the PLCB feature. Accordingly, this study uses $K=50$.

On the other hand, generalizing the best window size d is challenging. To avoid this challenge, this paper combines all candidates of d . [Fig. 3](#) shows the combination process that extracts PLCB features by different parameters and concatenates them. Single PLCBs have K

Fig. 3. Ensemble learning of parameter candidates.

Table 3
Investigated hyperparameters.

Parameters	Values
Number of clusters K	2, 3, 5, 8, 10, 16, 25, 50
Window size $d \times d$	2×2 , 3×3 , 5×5 , 7×7 , 11×11 , 15×15
Clustering algorithm	K-means, (GMM, Birch)
OCC algorithms	Classic, OCSVM, LOF, IF, GMM

Table 4
Comparison of sliding window size (K = 50).

Dataset	Method	2×2	3×3	5×5	7×7	11×11	15×15	All
MNIST	OCPLCB	72.08	76.23	79.55	82.25	85.07	79.17	85.19
	PLCB + OCSVM	68.05	71.10	74.97	78.41	90.57	90.53	82.93
	PLCB + LOF	78.58	84.70	91.99	95.35	96.31	95.14	97.71
	PLCB + IF	76.57	81.95	87.47	91.21	94.06	93.88	92.84
	PLCB + GMM	73.86	79.91	92.25	96.22	97.17	96.75	98.22
FMNIST	OCPLCB	72.33	74.32	77.54	77.76	77.91	81.25	78.84
	PLCB + OCSVM	73.79	74.57	77.81	79.61	82.35	86.06	81.68
	PLCB + LOF	82.19	83.73	87.48	87.43	86.54	83.63	90.80
	PLCB + IF	78.16	82.17	86.74	87.74	80.51	64.39	86.97
	PLCB + GMM	82.09	85.62	87.79	89.48	89.64	88.34	92.27
CIFAR10	OCPLCB	59.21	59.92	59.04	58.97	58.46	61.31	59.53
	PLCB + OCSVM	56.91	56.82	56.88	57.09	57.99	61.71	58.01
	PLCB + LOF	62.14	62.57	62.92	62.85	62.83	60.85	65.48
	PLCB + IF	67.11	65.93	65.05	61.09	55.50	49.78	64.32
	PLCB + GMM	63.63	64.93	65.95	66.07	64.42	60.52	68.19
CIFAR100	OCPLCB	57.46	57.06	56.76	56.32	55.89	55.52	57.09
	PLCB + OCSVM	56.68	56.39	56.64	56.52	56.67	56.26	57.25
	PLCB + LOF	60.85	60.36	60.04	59.66	59.18	58.29	62.92
	PLCB + IF	60.49	58.56	56.54	53.80	49.99	48.48	55.17
	PLCB + GMM	59.98	60.52	60.82	60.05	58.96	58.14	63.24
Kuzushiji49	OCPLCB	68.86	70.87	72.45	73.12	73.10	71.63	74.57
	PLCB + OCSVM	65.26	66.94	69.23	72.29	76.69	78.40	74.13
	PLCB + LOF	79.01	83.69	87.62	88.35	87.42	86.16	92.41
	PLCB + IF	72.41	75.16	76.83	77.83	81.30	79.78	80.61
	PLCB + GMM	66.01	70.36	77.61	81.16	85.29	88.30	87.35
X-ray (normal)	OCPLCB	73.50	71.32	70.46	72.78	72.36	70.38	73.86
	PLCB + OCSVM	74.48	73.34	71.68	75.32	76.60	75.98	77.46
	PLCB + LOF	72.96	73.44	73.08	74.94	78.08	78.58	78.88
	PLCB + IF	70.06	70.68	73.56	75.32	75.16	75.88	75.94
	PLCB + GMM	71.68	75.84	77.72	77.92	79.00	81.76	81.92
X-ray (Pneumonia)	OCPLCB	51.54	55.22	56.26	51.64	54.12	48.80	54.02
	PLCB + OCSVM	48.44	52.24	57.56	54.76	57.20	51.12	55.76
	PLCB + LOF	68.70	68.44	65.76	61.90	58.82	54.96	64.48
	PLCB + IF	74.54	70.78	65.46	55.70	57.46	53.80	66.52
	PLCB + GMM	66.88	64.56	60.86	54.90	55.40	52.34	66.52

dimension, while the final PLCB ($d = \text{all}$) has (number of candidates * k)-dimensions.

Table 4 reports AUC scores for OCPLCB, with the number of clusters K set at 50. The result is the average AUC score across all target classes. Moreover, the table separates the results for normal and pneumonia classes in the X-ray dataset, as the AUC scores exhibit significant differences.

Table 5 offers a comparison of the number of clusters. To facilitate this analysis, the best window sizes were selected. According to the findings in Table 4, an 11×11 window size is optimal for MNIST and FM-

NIST, while 7×7 performs the best for CIFAR10 and Kuzushiji49, and 2×2 is leading for CIFAR100. In the case of X-ray images, a 15×15 window size is the most suitable for normal X-ray images, while 2×2 is the best choice for pneumonia images. Note this experiment was done before the idea of an ensemble to avoid hyperparameter tuning.

According to the experimental results, GMM yields the highest AUC scores when paired with the PLCB feature.

4.3. Comparison

This section compares OCLCB with various other OCC algorithms. Table 6 summarizes OCC algorithms in the comparison, including their names, categorization (feature extraction or pretext tasks), and general hypotheses.

Table 7, Table 8, and Table 9 present comparative analyses of OCC algorithms for MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR10, respectively. AUC scores for the other methods are sourced from references [11,36,37].

Table 7 compares the MNIST dataset, where hyperparameters of OC-PLCB are window size = all and K = 50. IGD achieves the best result with an AUC of 99.3%, while PLCB + GMM remains competitive at 98.2%.

Table 8 offers a comparison focused on FMNIST. OCITN secures the best results. The performance gap between PLCB + GMM and Itrns is a 3.2% AUC score.

Table 9 compares AUC scores for CIFAR10. The best algorithms are self-supervised OCC algorithms, such as CSI, IGD, and GEO. In contrast, PLCB + GMM falls significantly short of the SOTA by 31%. The potential issues are that cluster balance depends on RGB information, and CIFAR10 images have diverse backgrounds containing different colors. OCPLCB and PLCB + OCC hold their ground in this competitive landscape, highlighting competitive performance compared to several other methods.

Table 10 compares the AUC scores for the CIFAR100 datasets. The reported score is the average of OCC results for all classes. Unlike the previous comparisons, this evaluation requires the implementation of additional algorithms. Therefore, many other OCC methods were not included due to the challenges and complexity of applying algorithms from unclear or unreleased source codes. The results of GEO, and CSI are based on the literature. OCPLCB outperforms OCAE and underperforms other methods.

Table 11 offers a comparative analysis focusing on chest X-ray pneumonia datasets. OCPLCB shows the best performance where one class is normal. Moreover, it exhibits competitive results where one class is pneumonia. Additionally, OCPLCB shows competitive performance for Kuzushiji49. The difference with ROT is 4.53%, a fair score without deep learning.

4.4. Experiment without resizing images

This subsection demonstrates the advantage of OCPLCB that the algorithm does not require resizing images. Although SOTA algorithms outperformed the OCPLCB in the experiments for resized images, these algorithms do not work without resizing. The experiment creates a randomly resized MNIST (RR-MNIST) and randomly resized CIFAR10 (RR-CIFAR10). In particular, all training and testing images were randomly resized into one of the following sizes (14×14 , 21×21 , 28×28 , 35×35 , 42×42 , 49×49 , 56×56). The clustering model is created from sliding windows of training data. Subsequently, sliding windows are assigned to clusters, and PLCB is computed. Afterward, the probability of clusters is calculated by dividing cluster balance by the number of sliding windows in the image. Accordingly, cluster balance is represented as probability. The hypothesis is that the probability is similar despite the image size. Then, the other process is the same as OCPLCB.

Table 12 provides experiment results for RR-MNIST. The experiment is performed with combining 2×2 , 3×3 , 5×5 , 7×7 , 11×11 windows and K = 50. PLCB + LOF shows 92.41% AUC, while other OCC algorithms struggle. The potential reason is that PLCB distributions differ

Table 5
Comparison of the number of clusters.

Dataset	Method	K=2	K=3	K=5	K=8	K=10	K=16	K=25	K=50
MNIST (11 × 11)	OCPLCB	68.76	69.2	73.73	79.05	79.70	81.05	83.46	85.07
	PLCB + OCSVM	68.59	72.81	79.12	83.49	84.57	87.62	89.72	90.57
	PLCB + LOF	58.03	66.84	81.02	88.89	91.81	94.52	95.63	96.31
	PLCB + IF	68.59	73.22	80.24	85.01	86.71	90.15	92.37	94.06
	PLCB + GMM	68.76	73.12	81.47	87.55	90.14	94.24	96.01	97.17
FMNIST (11 × 11)	OCPLCB	69.91	71.49	72.69	74.56	74.85	74.53	75.35	77.91
	PLCB + OCSVM	72.72	77.88	81.23	82.21	81.74	81.81	81.48	82.35
	PLCB + LOF	62.92	70.45	75.47	78.13	79.31	82.85	83.63	86.54
	PLCB + IF	75.23	82.19	86.35	87.23	87.83	88.16	86.94	80.51
	PLCB + GMM	69.91	78.29	82.28	83.39	83.62	86.14	87.59	89.61
CIFAR10 (7 × 7)	OCPLCB	54.09	54.43	54.73	56.00	56.54	57.36	57.88	58.97
	PLCB + OCSVM	54.17	55.31	55.40	56.46	56.90	57.19	57.00	57.99
	PLCB + LOF	51.16	51.80	56.90	60.65	61.64	63.31	63.34	63.49
	PLCB + IF	54.61	57.03	58.76	61.12	62.21	64.78	65.52	59.51
	PLCB + GMM	54.09	54.81	55.98	59.13	61.03	63.93	64.66	66.07
CIFAR100 (2 × 2)	OCPLCB	52.09	52.21	52.82	54.16	54.42	55.58	56.58	57.46
	PLCB + OCSVM	52.70	53.45	54.26	55.47	55.52	56.10	56.61	56.68
	PLCB + LOF	50.44	53.07	55.26	57.61	58.08	59.61	60.38	60.85
	PLCB + IF	53.23	54.60	53.69	54.64	55.46	56.18	58.18	60.49
	PLCB + GMM	52.09	52.60	53.60	55.23	55.32	56.37	58.24	59.98
Kuzushiji49 (7 × 7)	OCPLCB	59.96	61.55	65.35	67.50	68.26	70.22	71.67	73.12
	PLCB + OCSVM	60.17	62.77	67.05	68.49	69.23	70.93	71.64	72.29
	PLCB + LOF	53.80	59.34	72.17	76.07	78.24	83.12	85.60	88.35
	PLCB + IF	60.75	64.46	71.18	73.43	74.03	76.40	77.46	77.83
	PLCB + GMM	59.96	63.49	70.61	73.48	75.04	78.14	79.82	81.16
X-ray normal (15 × 15)	OCPLCB	56.02	56.50	55.90	64.32	67.52	69.96	71.58	70.38
	PLCB + OCSVM	56.20	58.78	59.20	68.22	71.06	73.38	76.72	75.98
	PLCB + LOF	52.54	60.04	68.06	65.24	68.84	75.36	78.62	78.58
	PLCB + IF	55.86	59.80	61.52	66.62	69.14	72.62	76.58	75.88
	PLCB + GMM	56.02	59.30	64.52	71.52	73.82	76.08	79.58	81.76
X-ray Pneumonia (2 × 2)	OCPLCB	46.00	45.68	45.72	44.66	43.14	45.80	46.88	51.54
	PLCB + OCSVM	46.60	44.80	47.84	47.30	43.96	46.66	45.78	48.44
	PLCB + LOF	48.28	49.14	56.92	60.50	62.36	66.50	66.74	68.70
	PLCB + IF	45.80	45.56	46.46	52.54	53.66	59.06	64.36	74.54
	PLCB + GMM	46.00	46.20	47.98	57.10	55.32	57.42	60.42	66.88

Table 6
Summary of compared algorithms.

Algorithm	Strategy	General hypothesis
DCAE [4]	Subtask	Reconstruction subtask with AE
ANOGAN [61]	Subtask	GAN subtask
DSVDD [11]	Feature extraction	Feature extraction with AE + SVDD
OCGAN [33]	Subtask	Reconstruction with GAN
ALOND [62]	Subtask	Classification between the original and reconstructed images.
ROT [40]	Subtask	Classification of rotations (four classes)
GEO [41]	Subtask	Classification of 72 geometric transformations
OCITN [37]	Subtask	Transforming all images to the same image.
ARAE [34]	Subtask	Reconstruction with adversarial example
AnoVit [35]	Subtask	Reconstruction with a transformer.
LSA [63]	Subtask	Novelty score = reconstruction error - likelihood of latent vector
IGD [25]	Feature extraction	Self-supervised feature extraction + GMM
CSI [42]	Subtask	Subtask to predict the shift and rotation
OCPLCB		Use PLCB as a feature vector.
PLCB + OCSVM		LCB feature extraction + OCSVM
PLCB + LOF	Feature extraction	LCB feature extraction + LOF.
PLCB + IF	(Proposal)	LCB feature extraction + IF.
PLCB + GMM		LCB feature extraction + GMM.

according to image sizes. LOF performs because it uses only the neighbor samples, perhaps the same size images.

Table 13 provides experiment results for RR-CIFAR10. Similarly, the experiment combined 2×2 , 3×3 , 5×5 , 7×7 , 11×11 windows and $K = 50$. While the AUC scores are better than random chance, they are not high. IF shows the best AUC score, likely due to its inherent randomness.

Since the clustering results cannot be controlled, the process is similar to a random function, aligning with the random tree for IF.

OCPLCB algorithm shows better than random AUCs without resizing. This is good start as the first size free OCC algorithm.

Table 14 reports the results with an X-ray pneumonia dataset. The data sizes vary: the height range is 127-2713, while the width range is 384-2916. We trained a K-means model using sliding windows on 50 training images due to limited memory space. PLCB features are extracted from training and testing images. Finally, OCC algorithms learned PLCB from the training images, and the models classified the test images. The experiment window sizes are 2×2 , 3×3 , 4×4 , 5×5 , and all combinations.

5. Discussion

This section provides various discussions. Subsection 5.1 analyzes time and space complexity. Subsection 5.2 executes ablation study to reduce sliding windows and accelerate OCPLCB. Subsection 5.3 discusses color information. Subsection 5.4 highlights the benefit of size-free, while subsection 5.5 lists limitations.

5.1. Computational complexity analysis

This subsection analyses time complexity and space complexity. Table 15 provides the training and testing time required to process class 0 for the MNIST and CIFAR datasets. The training data numbers are 6000 and 5000 samples, respectively, while both datasets include 10,000 testing images. The experiment was conducted in non-GPU environ-

Table 7
Comparison of OCC algorithms for MNIST.

Method	One class										Avg
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
DCAE	97.6	98.3	85.4	86.7	86.5	78.2	94.6	92.3	86.5	90.4	89.6
ANOGAN	96.6	99.2	85.0	88.7	89.4	88.3	94.7	93.5	84.9	92.4	91.3
DSVDD	98	99.7	91.7	91.9	94.9	88.5	98.3	94.6	93.9	96.5	94.8
OCGAN	99.8	99.9	94.2	96.3	97.5	98.0	99.1	98.1	93.9	98.1	97.5
ALOND	99.8	99.9	96.4	96.7	97.9	97.4	99.4	97.6	96.2	97.4	97.8
OCITNE	99.5	99.8	98	96.5	96.3	98.1	99.6	96.5	97.9	98.3	98.0
ARAE	99.8	99.9	96.0	97.2	97.0	97.4	99.5	96.9	92.4	98.5	97.5
AnoVit	98.0	98.6	91.1	83.8	91.3	92.4	97.5	91.4	83.8	95.8	92.4
LSA	99.3	99.9	95.9	96.6	95.6	96.4	99.4	98	95.3	98.1	97.5
IGD	99.8	99.9	99.2	99.1	99.3	99.1	99.7	99	98.5	99.1	99.3
OCPLCB	89.2	85.4	83.3	88.9	79.2	88.8	84.7	82.6	86.2	83.6	85.19
PLCB+OCSVM	88.4	94.5	78.9	82.1	78.8	79.0	81.2	82.9	82.7	81.7	82.93
PLCB+LOF	97.4	97.6	98.0	98.3	97.3	98.3	99.4	97.2	95.8	97.8	97.71
PLCB+IF	91.3	99.7	89.0	95.1	91.7	96.5	90.4	93.7	87.1	93.9	92.84
PLCB+GMM	99.6	99.8	97.1	98.6	97.3	98.6	99.2	97.7	96.6	97.7	98.22

Table 8
Comparison of OCC algorithms for FMNIST.

Method	One class										Avg
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
DSVDD	98.2	90.3	90.7	94.2	89.4	91.8	83.4	98.8	91.9	99.0	92.8
GEO	99.4	97.6	91.1	89.9	92.1	93.4	83.3	98.9	90.8	99.2	93.5
OCITN	95.6	99.1	93.3	96.3	93.6	95.5	85.4	98.8	98.0	98.9	95.5
ARAE	93.7	99.1	91.1	94.4	92.3	91.4	83.6	98.9	93.9	97.9	93.6
LSA	91.6	98.3	87.8	92.3	89.7	90.7	84.1	97.7	91.0	98.4	92.2
IGD	92.5	99.2	92.5	93.8	92.9	98.2	87.9	99.0	94.3	97.5	94.5
OCPLCB	67.4	95.0	59.4	78.7	75.2	95.5	49.2	96.9	75.5	95.6	78.84
PLCB+OCSVM	69.9	96.6	71.4	80.3	75.4	93.9	58.8	97.1	77.4	96.0	81.68
PLCB+LOF	87.0	92.4	86.9	92.7	88.2	93.9	80.4	96.5	92.2	97.8	90.80
PLCB+IF	82.3	93.3	74.9	87.3	85.0	92.4	73.9	97.4	85.7	97.5	86.97
PLCB+GMM	90.5	97.3	85.8	94.7	91.1	93.6	81.2	98.0	91.8	98.7	92.27

Table 9
Comparison of OCC algorithms for CIFAR10.

Method	One class										Avg
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
DCAE	59.1	57.4	48.9	58.4	54.0	62.2	51.2	58.6	76.8	67.3	59.4
ANOGAN	67.1	54.7	52.9	54.5	65.1	60.3	58.5	62.5	75.8	66.5	61.8
DSVDD	61.7	65.9	50.8	59.1	60.9	65.7	67.7	67.3	75.9	73.1	64.8
OCELM	75.0	66.0	59.3	59.7	69.8	61.1	73.9	62.9	78.4	76.5	68.2
OCGAN	75.7	53.1	64.0	62.0	72.3	62.0	57.5	72.3	82.0	55.4	65.6
ALOND	78.2	71.7	65.5	65.4	73.4	66.6	78.4	68.3	81.3	73.8	72.2
GEO	74.7	95.7	78.1	72.4	87.8	87.8	83.4	95.5	93.3	91.3	86.0
OCITNE	79.6	89.9	70.4	61.9	72.6	74.6	81.4	82.6	85.0	86.4	78.4
ARAE	72.2	43.1	69.0	55.0	75.2	54.7	70.1	51.0	72.2	40.0	60.2
AnoVit	66.4	46.4	63.9	55.0	74.3	54.2	70.0	50.9	69.7	50.2	60.1
LSA	73.5	58.0	69.0	54.2	76.1	54.6	75.1	53.5	71.7	54.8	64.1
IGD	90.6	97.7	83.9	82.3	88.6	89.9	90.9	96.4	96.9	94.8	91.2
CSI	89.9	99.1	93.1	86.4	93.9	93.2	95.1	98.7	97.9	95.5	94.3
OCPLCB	44.9	74.7	41.3	59.3	48.4	62.1	57.3	66.3	64.0	77.0	59.53
PLCB+OCSVM	41.8	75.8	37.8	59.9	44.8	62.4	53.5	66.3	61.6	76.2	58.01
PLCB+LOF	48.6	83.0	53.1	65.9	52.0	68.5	66.5	68.5	67.5	81.2	65.48
PLCB+IF	62.0	70.3	62.1	53.7	71.0	56.4	74.5	63.7	68.8	70.7	64.32
PLCB+GMM	57.7	76.3	56.0	66.8	65.4	67.0	76.9	65.7	74.0	76.1	68.19

ments with the following characteristics: Intel® Core™i9-9900 K CPU @ 3.60 GHz and 64 GB RAM.

The training process involves fitting clustering algorithms, extracting PLCB, and fitting OCC algorithms. In contrast, the testing process applies a clustering model, PLCB feature extraction, and OCC models. The bottleneck is fitting the clustering model. One can ignore OCC algorithms as their processing times are relatively short (OCSVM takes 1.1 seconds in the testing stage, while other algorithms require less time).

The training stage takes longer than the testing stage because it requires additional time to fit the clustering model. Applying a pretrained clustering model could accelerate the method. Moreover, this processing time is comparable to simple neural network architectures, such as AE or CNN. The proposal and these neural network-based methods have a common aspect of working with sliding windows.

Suppose input image size as $M \times M \times C$ and using OCPLCB with $d \times d$ sliding windows and K clusters, training stage is approximately $O(nKd^2(M-d+1)^2)$, which is computed from the multiplication of k

Table 10
Comparison of OCC algorithms for CIFAR100.

Method	AUC
OCAE	58.12
OCITN	69.22
ROT	72.46
GEO	78.70
CSI	89.60
OCPLCB	57.09
PLCB + OCSVM	57.25
PLCB + LOF	62.92
PLCB + IF	55.17
PLCB + GMM	63.24

Table 11
Comparison of OCC algorithms for X-ray and Kuzushiji49 dataset.

Method	X-ray		Kuzushiji49
	One = normal	One = Pneumonia	
OCAE	61.9±4.9	76.7±0.4	68.72
OCITN	79.6±2.2	44.1±3.1	94.11
ROT	76.5±6.0	34.9±6.5	96.94
OCPLCB	73.9±0.2	54.0±0.5	74.57
PLCB + OCSVM	77.5±0.2	55.8±0.3	74.13
PLCB + LOF	78.9±0.1	64.5±0.7	92.41
PLCB + IF	75.9±1.7	66.5±2.7	80.61
PLCB + GMM	81.9±0.5	66.5±0.5	87.35

Fig. 4. The scale of time complexity.

means' time complexity $O(nK)$ and number of sliding windows $(M - d + 1)^2$, and these dimension d^2 . Note that k-means has another metric iteration i . However, this value is not clear because number of iterations differs in every execution. The testing stage has time complexity: $O(nd^2(M - d + 1)^2)$.

Fig. 4 visualizes the time complexity scale for image size $M \times M$, where $n = 1$, $d = 15$, and $K = 50$. Moreover, the red line shows $M = 28$ (size of MNIST). Both training and testing complexity scales with the square of image sizes, where training complexity is K times larger than testing complexity for training k-means clustering model. This theory align with the actual result reported in Table 15, where the training time is larger than K times of testing time.

Subsequently, Table 16 analyzes the required memory space for processing a single image, which contains 784 values with the shape $28 \times 28 \times 1$. Moreover, the PLCB feature is represented as a K -dimensional vector. The memory space for sliding windows is the most crucial factor affecting processing time. Furthermore, the number of windows will increase exponentially with image size.

Fig. 5. The scale of space complexity.

The space complexity is approximately $O(nd^2(M - d + 1)^2)$ for handling the sliding windows. On the other hand, the final PLCB features will be $O(nK)$, which might be multiplied by the number of combined hyperparameters.

Fig. 5 simulates space complexity of sliding windows for image sizes $M \times M$, where $d = 15$ and $n = 1$. The red line shows $M = 28$, which is the size of the MNIST dataset.

Note that the time and space complexity change when different clustering algorithms are applied instead of k-means. GMM is a clustering algorithm based on Gaussian Mixture. Its time complexity is $O(n^3)$ [58], which is quite large and unsuitable for clustering sliding windows. On the other hand, the time complexity of Birch is $O(n)$ [58], which is faster than k-means. However, Birch has an issue with scalability for space complexity. According to scikit-learn documentation [60], the algorithm will struggle to process more than 20 dimensions, which makes it challenging to process large windows. Practically, both GMM and Birch caused memory errors when analyzing large sliding windows. Moreover, increasing the step size of sliding windows can reduce the computation cost. The detail is discussed in the next subsection. In addition, the future work could apply dimension reduction or sample (sliding windows) reduction strategies to reduce the computation cost.

5.2. The experiment with different step sizes

One possible acceleration strategy is to increase the step sizes S for sliding windows. Such a process can reduce both time and space complexities for S^2 times. However, the performance degradation is not clear. Accordingly, Table 17 reports an ablation study to analyze the number of step sizes. The experiment utilized the MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR10 datasets. The original step size is 1, while the experiment prepared step sizes 2, 3, 5, 7, and 10. Approximately, the number of sliding windows is reduced S^2 times, while the AUC scores degrade accordingly. The degradations from $S = 1$ to $S = 2$ were statistically confirmed by the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with p-values of 0.002, 0.041, and 0.216 for MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR10, respectively.

Table 18 reports the same ablation study for the size free X-ray image dataset. $S = 1$ is reported in Table 14 (All). Other alternatives reduced the sliding windows by increasing step sizes. Overall, the experiment results are similar, while processing speed is improved for the square of step size times.

Table 19 shows p-values of Wilcoxon signed-ranked test for step size changes. When one class is normal, $S = 10$ outperformed $S = 1$ ($p = 0.001$). On the other hand, when one class was pneumonia, the result with $S = 10$ underperformed $S = 1$ ($p = 0.035$).

MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR10 were relatively small datasets. Therefore, increasing skip size causes the problem. On the other hand, the

Table 12
Experiment results for RR-MNIST.

Algorithm	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Avg
OCPLCB	63.8	67.6	63.5	64.7	60.6	64.0	61.1	54.2	64.6	59.5	62.36
PLCB + OCSVM	68.5	55.6	63.0	59.2	55.2	58.6	56.9	49.9	62.2	52.0	58.04
PLCB + LOF	94.5	93.6	87.5	95.0	93.2	92.7	91.8	89.8	93.4	92.6	92.41
PLCB + IF	56.7	92.9	63.1	67.9	66.0	71.5	64.0	69.4	62.8	68.1	68.24
PLCB + GMM	61.1	90.3	59.5	66.8	67.4	65.9	63.5	68.8	61.3	67.1	67.17

Table 13
Experiment results for RR-CIFAR10.

Algorithm	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Avg
OCPLCB	44.9	71.3	42.2	57.3	48.8	60.0	57.1	65.0	63.3	74.1	58.4
PLCB + OCSVM	39.5	72.2	37.8	58.2	46.0	60.2	54.7	64.4	60.3	74.1	56.7
PLCB + LOF	44.3	74.2	51.8	60.2	54.1	61.9	60.4	63.3	64.7	73.1	60.8
PLCB + IF	63.2	67.6	58.3	57.2	67.1	51.5	68.5	56.1	70.2	69.2	62.9
PLCB + GMM	48.5	65.6	46.6	58.7	56.7	59.3	62.5	60.9	64.3	67.7	59.1

Table 14
Experiment results for unresized X-ray images.

One	Algorithm	Resized	Size free				
		All	2×2	3×3	4×4	5×5	All
Normal	OCPLCB	73.9±0.2	73.3±0.3	73.4±0.0	73.3±0.2	73.4±0.3	73.1±0.1
	PLCB + OCSVM	77.5±0.2	72.3±0.4	72.4±0.8	71.7±0.8	71.8±0.4	72.0±0.2
	PLCB + LOF	78.9±0.1	74.6±1.3	75.4±0.4	74.6±1.5	75.1±0.4	74.1±0.8
	PLCB + IF	75.9±1.7	68.7±1.8	68.7±2.2	69.8±1.0	70.2±1.5	67.9±1.3
	PLCB + GMM	81.9±0.5	74.8±0.8	74.9±1.0	75.2±1.2	75.7±0.7	74.2±1.4
Pneumonia	OCPLCB	54.0±0.5	39.2±0.3	39.5±0.4	39.1±0.4	38.9±0.1	38.9±0.2
	PLCB + OCSVM	55.8±0.3	42.1±0.8	42.5±1.5	43.7±0.7	42.0±0.7	42.1±0.5
	PLCB + LOF	64.5±0.7	67.9±0.5	67.9±0.7	67.9±0.5	67.8±0.3	67.8±0.5
	PLCB + IF	66.5±2.7	58.4±2.9	58.5±2.5	58.0±3.9	58.7±2.8	52.9±2.9
	PLCB + GMM	66.5±0.5	40.6±1.3	40.7±1.3	39.8±1.0	39.8±0.7	36.7±1.3

Table 15
The processing time with different hyperparameters (seconds).

Hyperparameters	MNIST (28×28×1)		CIFAR10 (32×32×3)	
	Training	Testing	Training	Testing
2×2, K=50	10.2	1.9	18.7	3.0
3×3, K=50	10.1	2.1	23.6	4.0
5×5, K=50	22.5	2.7	44.8	6.2
7×7, K=50	25.6	3.4	149.0	9.3
11×11, K=50	45.7	4.9	186.0	14.7
15×15, K=2	6.7	5.3	25.4	18.9
15×15, K=5	10.1	5.3	25.5	19.0
15×15, K=10	12.9	5.1	36.7	19.0
15×15, K=25	17.4	5.1	156.8	19.1
15×15, K=50	48.1	5.4	186.0	18.9
Ensemble, K=50	162.3	20.4	510.6	56.1

Table 16
Space complexity for a single image.

Hyperparameter	Input shape	Sliding windows	PLCB shape
2×2, K=50		2916 (27×27×4)	
3×3, K=50		6084 (26×26×9)	
5×5, K=50		14,400 (24×24×25)	50
7×7, K=50		21,609 (21×21×49)	
11×11, K=50		39,204 (18×18×121)	
15×15, K=2	784 (28×28×1)		2
15×15, K=5			5
15×15, K=10		44,100(14×14×225)	10
15×15, K=25			25
15×15, K=50			50
Ensemble, K=50		128,313 (summation)	300 (50×6)

unresized X-ray images are quite large. Therefore, skipping a few pixels does not make a significant difference.

5.3. Successful OCC requires features unrelated to color

OCPLCB achieves fair AUC scores for MNIST, FMNIST, Kuzushiji49, and X-ray pneumonia datasets. However, its performance in CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 falls short due to the diverse colors of the foreground and background. Since the clustering model input consists of sliding windows composed of pixels, the PLCB feature is related to color information.

In comparisons of color image datasets, successful algorithms disregard color information. For instance, classification of rotations [40] or geometric transformations [41] are not related to color.

Furthermore, ablation studies by Tack et al. [42] support this hypothesis, in which transformations unrelated to color (rotation and permutation) outperformed those related to color (Sobel, noise, and blur).

In addition, this hypothesis can explain the success of deep learning in images: deeper layers can extract features unrelated to color, as they are far from pixel values.

In summary, the current OCPLCB algorithm extracts feature vectors related to color information, which degrades the classification of color image datasets. The potential solutions are 1) ignoring color information by a deeper architecture and 2) replacing the clustering model with alternative models unrelated to color information.

5.4. Benefit of size-free OCC

A size-free function offers several benefits for future work. First, a single model can classify images of various sizes without the system error. Potential use cases include all possible unresized image datasets. For example, object detection classifies bounding boxes of various sizes. Although existing size-free algorithms [53,54] have already achieved this goal, OCPLCB offers an alternative solution using clustering and OCC.

Table 17
Ablation studies of step sizes S (PLCB + GMM).

MNIST	One class										Avg	Time (s/class)
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9		
S=1	99.6	99.8	97.1	98.7	97.3	98.6	99.2	97.7	96.6	97.7	98.22	162.3
S=2	98.5	99.8	92.0	96.2	94.9	96.6	97.9	95.7	91.1	95.9	95.86	41.5
S=3	98.0	99.8	88.0	93.7	92.7	95.1	96.7	94.2	87.6	94.9	94.07	17.5
S=5	97.3	99.9	85.5	93.1	93.6	93.2	97.3	95.7	85.4	95.6	93.66	6.42
S=7	98.4	99.8	84.8	85.6	94.7	91.7	96.8	94.1	85.7	95.9	92.75	2.51
S=10	96.8	99.3	85.0	83.4	91.8	90.5	96.2	93.1	79.7	93.2	90.90	1.33

FMNIST	One class										Avg	Time (s/class)
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9		
S=1	90.5	97.3	85.8	94.7	91.1	93.6	81.2	98.0	91.8	98.7	92.27	153.1
S=2	89.5	97.3	84.8	94.4	90.0	92.9	82.3	97.8	89.4	98.5	91.69	34.6
S=3	89.2	97.4	84.2	94.1	89.9	92.3	82.0	97.9	88.6	98.3	91.39	13.9
S=5	87.6	97.6	86.8	93.3	90.4	91.6	81.4	97.9	86.4	98.2	91.12	4.40
S=7	89.0	98.1	87.7	92.1	91.9	91.6	81.2	97.8	85.1	97.9	91.24	2.49
S=10	84.0	97.7	85.3	91.9	90.5	90.1	75.3	97.6	78.0	97.2	88.76	1.56

CIFAR10	One class										Avg	Time (s/class)
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9		
S=1	57.7	76.3	56.0	66.8	65.4	67.0	76.9	65.7	74.0	76.1	68.19	510.6
S=2	58.5	73.4	59.3	65.8	66.5	66.1	76.6	63.9	73.6	73.9	67.76	124.5
S=3	58.0	70.6	59.1	65.0	67.0	63.4	75.7	61.0	73.9	71.2	66.49	49.0
S=5	59.0	66.3	60.6	64.1	68.4	62.9	75.0	57.2	73.9	65.7	65.31	21.4
S=7	59.2	62.2	59.9	60.5	69.6	59.0	74.5	54.5	74.5	61.7	63.56	8.7
S=10	60.5	55.3	61.9	60.6	70.3	56.5	72.3	52.9	75.6	58.4	62.43	4.9

Table 18
Ablation studies for unresized X-ray images.

One	Algorithm	S=1	S=2	S=3	S=5	S=7	S=10
Normal	OCPLCB	73.4±0.1	73.3±0.1	73.3±0.1	73.4±0.0	73.5±0.0	73.6±0.2
	PLCB + OCSVM	72.0±0.2	71.9±0.1	72.0±0.3	72.2±0.1	72.4±0.3	72.5±0.1
	PLCB + LOF	74.4±0.8	73.5±0.8	74.0±0.6	73.9±0.5	74.1±0.7	74.1±0.6
	PLCB + IF	68.9±1.3	70.2±0.9	69.0±1.6	69.5±1.4	69.0±1.3	70.3±1.3
	PLCB + GMM	73.4±1.4	72.7±1.5	73.1±1.0	73.7±0.8	73.7±0.6	76.1±1.0
Pneumonia	OCPLCB	39.2±0.2	39.4±0.2	39.4±0.3	39.2±0.1	39.1±0.3	38.9±0.1
	PLCB + OCSVM	42.1±0.5	43.0±0.7	43.9±0.4	42.8±0.6	43.3±0.4	42.8±0.4
	PLCB + LOF	67.8±0.5	68.9±0.5	69.6±0.5	68.6±0.6	68.8±0.5	68.8±0.8
	PLCB + IF	52.9±2.9	58.5±1.3	58.7±2.5	56.2±2.0	59.6±3.3	58.0±2.0
	PLCB + GMM	36.7±1.3	39.2±1.1	37.7±1.1	34.8±1.3	33.8±1.1	29.1±1.6

Table 19
P-values of Wilcoxon signed-rank test for step size changes.

Normal	S=1	S=2	S=3	S=5	S=7	S=10	Pneumonia	S=1	S=2	S=3	S=5	S=7	S=10
S=1	-	0.237	0.195	0.692	0.671	0.999	S=1	-	0.871	0.93	0.112	0.251	0.035
S=2	0.763	-	0.487	0.873	0.888	0.994	S=2	0.129	-	0.686	0.001	0.069	0.015
S=3	0.805	0.513	-	0.749	0.921	0.997	S=3	0.07	0.314	-	<0.001	0.002	<0.001
S=5	0.308	0.127	0.251	-	0.792	1	S=5	0.888	0.999	1	-	0.701	0.053
S=7	0.329	0.112	0.079	0.208	-	0.997	S=7	0.749	0.931	0.998	0.299	-	0.007
S=10	0.001	0.006	0.003	<0.001	0.003	-	S=10	0.965	0.985	1	0.947	0.993	-

Second, image datasets can ignore image size for normalizing other metrics. Traditional image datasets sacrificed the normality of different aspects, such as resolution or image entropy, to normalize image size. Future work can do the opposite; for example, resizing images could equalize image entropy [64].

Third, a size-free algorithm can classify images based on their sizes. Although checking image shapes is a faster solution, the idea could lead to a new self-labeled classification subtask to classify image.

Additionally, one can extend OCPLCB to time-series data. OCC/Su-supervised classification between different signal lengths should be an interesting direction. Moreover, an ensemble of window sizes could improve the performance of time series data.

5.5. Limitations

OCPLCB has three fundamental limitations. The first issue is the scalability of processing large images, as described in subsection 5.1. Faster

clustering algorithms could address the problem. One idea is to apply random functions for clustering. Moreover, sliding windows should be carefully treated to avoid memory errors.

The second problem is the low AUC in the color dataset. OC-PLCB cannot address this problem because 1) clustering automatically extracts features related to color information, and 2) one cannot control unsupervised clustering results. Fortunately, the size-free function is not related to clustering. Therefore, substituting the clustering model with a different model could address the issue. The promising idea is a self-supervised classification of sliding windows.

Third, determining the optimal hyperparameter is impossible during training because OCC algorithms cannot access multiple classes. Combining all hyperparameters is a straightforward solution. However, it is impossible due to time, and the range of hyperparameters must be defined. In addition, the relation between feature vectors and image sizes is not yet clear.

Future work can address this question through OCC, with subtasks for size classification. Moreover, this study did not provide experiments for an ensemble of K or a combination of K and d.

6. Conclusion

This study proposes a size-free OCC approach, namely OCPLCB. Size-free methods offer various benefits for future image classification. Moreover, the proposed approach applies ensemble learning of all hyperparameter candidates. OCPLCB with ensemble of hyperparameters shows a fair AUC score for grayscale images. However, OCPLCB underperformed in color images. The experimental results suggest that successful OCC algorithms require features unrelated to color information. Traditional deep learning automatically extracts the features that contribute to classification, whereas unsupervised clustering cannot select such feature. Future work should apply alternative methods to sliding windows.

The future works are categorized into 1) improve the accuracy metric of size-free OCC, 2) address the scalability issue, and 3) apply size-free functions to the theory or real-world applications. Accuracy could be improved by applying supervised learning to sliding windows, extending other size-free techniques to OCC, and considering subtasks to sliding windows. On the other hand, there are three general solutions to improve scalability: applying algorithms faster than K-means, reducing the sliding window size (data reduction), and dimension reduction. The third group includes a size classification subtask and applying size-free OCC algorithms to challenging real-world scenarios.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Toshitaka Hayashi: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization; **Dalibor Cimr:** Writing – original draft; **Hamido Fujita:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision; **Richard Cimler:** Resources.

Data availability

The datasets are explained in the paper. Source code is uploaded at <https://github.com/ToshiHayashi/OCPLCB>.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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